

Dairy Development in India

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Abstract- India is the largest producer of milk in the world and it is also largest consumer of milk consuming almost its whole milk production. Dairy industry in India is one of the important contributors in the India GDP. India dairy have played important role in the rural development of India and has shaped lives of millions of dairy farmers. The present study analyzes the growth and development of Indian dairy industry and challenges faced by it. Government agencies and policymakers of India have started various dairy development programs for the development of Indian dairy industry such Key Villages Scheme, Intensive Cattle Development Program and Operation Flood. These dairy development programs have written the success story of Indian dairy development and have played important role in becoming self-reliant in dairy production. Although India is self-reliant in dairy production but its dairy industry is facing challenges also such as small size of herds, lack of investment, prevention of disease in animals, inefficiency of organized sector etc. The present paper highlight the development of dairy industry, employment creation, fund allocation and also problems of dairy industry in India.

Indexed Terms- Dairy Industry, Problems, Development

I. INTRODUCTION

Dairy farming has been an important part of the agricultural scenario for thousands of years. India being a predominantly agrarian economy has about 70 per cent of its population living in villages, where livestock play a crucial role in the socio-economic life. Livestock provide high-quality foods such as milk, cheese, butter, ghee, etc. India is not only one of the top producers of milk in the world, but also the largest

consumer of milk and milk products in the world. Due to the shortfall in supply, we have to import significant amounts of milk products to meet internal demand.

Agriculture and animal husbandry have a symbiotic relationship, in which the agricultural sector provides feed and fodder for the livestock and animals provide milk, manure and draught power for various agricultural operations. Dairy sector is instrumental in bringing socio-economic transformation in India. It has created a lot of employment opportunities and also provides improved nutritional benefits.

Importance of dairy farming Milk is a wholesome food among all the animal products. It contains in proper proportions the various essential food ingredients required by human body in an easily digestible form. Inclusion of milk in the human diet increases the digestibility of other types of food as well. The productivity of milk varies in different countries, as some countries are surplus in production, some are deficit in production, and in some of the countries, availability matches their requirement.

The demand for milk is constantly increasing in cities as well as small towns and rural areas. The factors influencing this increased demand are — rapid increase in population, spread of education, growing nutritional awareness and improved purchasing power of consumers. Dairy farming in India has evolved from just an agrarian way of life to a professionally managed industry. A large number of rural families in India are engaged in dairy production, for whom this is an important source of secondary income. In India, raw milk is perceived to be fresh by most consumers and has a large market. Conventional dietary habits in India account for about 60 per cent of milk consumption in liquid form, and the remaining in the form of ghee, cheese, curd, paneer, ice cream, dairy

whiteners and traditional sweets. Dairying provides a source of daily income with a relatively low level of risk. Most of the dairy farmers in India raise animals at a small scale in traditional ways. The productivity of these farmers can be enhanced if they run their business in a scientific manner. Most of such farmers are not aware of the modern methods of dairy farming. As a result, some farmers lose their investment instead of making profit. To ensure maximum production and profits from dairy farming, it is essential that these farmers adopt proper business plans and good dairy management practices.

II. OBJECTIVES

1. To study the importance of Dairy sector
2. To discuss the dairy development in India

III. METHODOLOGY

This paper is only enlighten secondary data sources only. The data pertaining from various sources like annual reports, books, journals and various libraries, collected, presented and analysed hereunder.

Employment potential in dairying

India’s share in the world milk trade is quite low, and compared to the total milk produced, only small quantity of it is processed. In the informal sector, milk vendors collect milk from local producers and sell it in urban and semi-urban areas. These milk vendors handle around 65–70 per cent of the total milk production. The increase in human population has a direct effect on the demand for food. However, globally there is shrinkage of cultivable lands, which makes the role of livestock sector even more important, not only in terms of nutritional security but also employment generation. The Agricultural and Processed Food Products Export Development Authority (APEDA) is the regulator for import and export of dairy products in India. Indian milk desserts are quite popular with many communities, including the Indians settled abroad. A good example of this is the rasgulla, which has earned a place of honour as a sweet meat worldwide. It is clear that the demand for such products is expected to increase in future, thereby boosting the potential for export. Considering the production economics of dairy products globally, countries which have low cost of milk production such

as India are expected to derive maximum benefit from the booming dairy upsurge. Thus, from the emerging scenario in the dairy sector, nationally as well as internationally, it is evident that a lot of employment generation and potential for entrepreneurial activities exist in the dairy sector.

Table 1
Live stock population in India

S.No	Particulars	Live stock census 2012	Census 2019	Growth rate
1	Cattle	190.90	193.46	1.34
2	Buffalo	108.70	109.85	1.06
3	Yaks	0.08	0.06	-24.90
4	Mithun	0.30	0.39	29.52
	Total bovines	299.98	303.76	1.26
5	Sheept	65.07	74.26	14.13
6	Goat	135.17	148.88	10.14
7	Pigs	10.29	9.06	-12.03
8	Other animals	1.54	0.79	-48.70
9	Poultry	729.21	851.81	16.81

Source: Annual Report, 2022-23

As per the provisional estimates of Gross Value Added (GVA) of MoSPI released on 31st May, 2024 the Gross Value Added (GVA) of livestock sector is about Rs 13,55,460 crores at current prices during FY 2022-23 which is about 30.23 % of Agricultural & Allied Sector GVA and 5.50 % of Total GVA. At constant prices (2011-12), the GVA of Livestock Sector is about Rs 6,90,268 crores during FY 2022- 23 with a positive growth of 5.02% over previous financial year.

Table 2

Status of National Action Plan for Dairy Development in India (2016-2017 to 2023-2024)			
Particulars	2015-16	2023-24	ADDNL/ GAP
Population (In Billion)	1254	1389.4	135.4
Milk Pron (MNT)	160.4	300	139.6
Per Capita Consumption (Liter/Yr)	127.8	215.9	88.1

In Milch Bovines (Mn)	91.8	116.4	24.6
Yelld/Bovine	4.6	7.1	2.4
Procurement Quantity	-	-	-
Total			
Qty (In LLPD)	2284.6	4931.5	2646.9
Value (Rs. in Crore)	648.4	2281.5	1633.1
Cooperative			
Qty (In LLPD)	440.7	1643.8	1203.2
Value (Rs. in Crore)	141.9	781.8	640
Pvt.			
Qty (In LLPD)	430	2465.8	2035.8
Value (Rs. in Crore)	138.4	1172.7	1034.3
Mpo			
Qty (In LLPD)	20	150	130
Value (Rs. in Crore)	6.4	71.3	64.9
Uo			
Qty (In LLPD)	1404.6	671.9	-732.7
Value (Rs. in Crore)	361.7	255.7	-106.1
Total Transportation			
Qty (In LLPD)	-	4931.5	4932
Cost (Rs. in Crore)	-	7668.3	50236.4
Processing			
Qty (In LLPD)	1413	3924.8	2511.8
Cost (Rs. in Crore)	28259.6	7849.6	50236.4
Chilling			
Qty (In LLPD)	759.6	3493	2733.4
Cost (Rs. in Crore)	3798.2	1746.4.9	13666.8
Value Added Products			

Qty (MTPD)	7918.1	2053.4	12615.9
Cost (Rs. in Crore)	1979.5	5133.5	3154
Drying Capacity (MTPD)			
Total	3057	8496	5439
Cooperative	1592	2182	590
Pvt.	1465	6164	150
Mpo	0	150	150
Cattle Feed Plant Capacity (MTPD)			
Total	15333	21300	5967
Cooperative	15662	18361	26699
Pvt.	-	2699	2699
Mpo	-	240	240
Milk Producers (In Lakh)			
Total	800	800	0
Cooperative	1550	208	53
Pvt.	50.2	164.4	114.2
Mpo	3.3	15	11.7
Uo	591.5	412.6	-178.9
Dairy Cooperatives/Coll ection Centers (In Lakh)			
Total	3.2	8.3	5.1
Cooperative	1.7	3.3	1.6
Pvt.	1.4	4.7	3.3
Mpo	0.1	0.3	0.2
Milk Supplied (In LLPD)			
Total	2264	3987	1723.1
Cooperative	418	1561.6	1143.6
Pvt.	21.4	1611	1189.6
Mpo	20	142.5	122.5
Uo	1404.6	671.9	-

The above table demonstrated that the status of national Action plan for dairy development in India

from 2016-17 to 2023-24 financial year in India. It can be noticed that total population are 1254 million in 2015-16 financial year while 1389.4 billion population in 2023-24 . In case of milk production 2015-16 is found 160.4 mnt while 2023-24 financial year were noticed that 300 mnt. It is further discloses that per capita consumption (litre/yr) was found 127.8 in 2015-16 and 215.9 in 2023-24 financial year in the study area. It is another aspects, total milk products producers through cooperatives 1550 lakhs in 2015-16 and 208 lakhs in 2023-24, private organisation 50.2 lakhs in 2015-16 and 164.4 lakhs in 2023-24, Mpo 3.3 lakhs in 2015-16 and 15 lakhs in 2013-24 and Uo 591.5 lakhs in 2015-16 and 412.6 in 2023-24 financial year respectively.

State/UTs	2014-2015	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020	2020-2021	2021-2022	2022-2023	Utilised	UnSpent
Andhra Pradesh	0	350.31	435.68	621.56	70.66	878.53	0	6.72	0	2363.46	0
Arunachal Pradesh	94	372.31	242.03	0	0	0	0	0	0	708.34	64.71
Assam	0	98.401	0	0	0	82.72	0	0	0	181.12	0
Bihar	300	1058.492	1287.34	3284.7	3793.47	1902.58	2544.2	2.42	0	14173.2	3149.94
Chhattisgarh	149.95	204.25	65.13	0	0	230.11	0	0	0	649.44	110.2
Goa	0	0	0	43.48	0	41.15	0	0	0	84.63	748.02
Gujarat	119.6		0	947.16	3580.47	588.31	160.71	32.44	0	5428.25	4468.9
Haryana	0	27.93	0	274.8	161.99	415.44	0	0.87	0	881.03	538.49
Himachal Pradesh	0	0	0	49.98	1243.32	61.54	39.64	12.14	0.5	1407.12	1262.91
Jammu & Kashmir	365.27	0	504.87	100	1539.35	672.13	949.52	41.56	0	4172.7	1539.35
Jharkhand	0	0	160.87	0	0	87	0	0	3.22	251.09	147.25
Karnataka	199.87	445.8	0	260	1011	2018	1128.14	32.39	6.72	5101.92	115.5
Kerala	2523.5	105.97	1305.03	543.77	2381.24	2947.46	600.95	13.98	0.3	10422.2	1777.67
Madhya Pradesh	0	363.55	155.21	358.83	2085.27	1503.33	0	0	0	4466.19	847.29
Maharashtra	119.7	0	0	0	184.12	902.48	285.67	0	0	1491.97	202.51
Manipur	257.6	0	0	297.5	51.09	575.76	510.65	0	0	1692.6	4.99
Meghalaya	0	0	0	386.59	427.77	628.17	425.67	8.11	9.92	1886.23	160.99
Mizoram	17.42	0	438.47	310.3	0	579.58	17.65	0	0	1363.42	0
Nagaland	189.56	100	100	111.95	0	349.8	0	2	0	853.31	0
Odisha	306.99	1066.92	1242.88	0	801.28	747.11	0	1.91	0	4167.09	416.98
Puducherry	0	0	0	0	0	42.5	0	0.39	0	42.89	240.15
Punjab	760.31	2092.29	1777.95	1089.11	368.83	1311.75	186.56	29.54	0	7616.34	168.83
Rajasthan	115.97	230.15	902.39	1899.843	4281.78	2406.7	1229.95	22.03	8.78	11097.59	1760

Sikkim	199.43	338.69	436.31	487.97	0	263.95	1006.28	6.37	4.72	2743.72	105.64
Tamil Nadu	1500.75	200	689.73	762.5	759.62	107.48	732.03	2.6	27.61	4782.32	1190.42
Telangana	0	292.46	432.2	275.85	0	844.1	919.75	0	0	2764.36	0
Tripura	642.17	0	0	0	314.15	5.32	4.09	0	0	965.73	1337.14
Uttar Pradesh	263.19	115.93	252.06	0	0	82.78	0	0	0	713.96	3406.36
Uttarakhand	800	0	702.79	877.85	0	1643.71	0	1.48	0	4025.83	302.03
West Bengal	51.96	0	0	183.57	0.004	101.79	0	0.71	0	338.03	0
India	8976.8	7365.05	11229.34	13167.3	23055.42	22021.28	10741.47	217.66	61.78	96836.1	24066.24

Note: 1: Rs. 370.09 lakh released during 2016-17 was refunded.

2 : Rs. 833.94 lakh released during 2016-17 was refunded by Bihar.

3 : Rs. 29.152 lakh was refunded by Rajasthan for the release made during 2017-18.

4 : Rs. 6.78 lakh refunded by West Bengal during 2018-19.

5 : Rs. In Crore

Source: Lok sabha unstarred Question No.440, dated on 25.06.2019..

Lok sabha Unstarred Question No. 2142, dated on 15.03.2022.

Lok sabha Unstarred Question No. 3213, dated on 15.03.2022.

Lok sabha Unstarred Question No. 3217, dated on 08.08.2023.

Table demonstrated that state wise funds utilised under national programme for dairy development (NPDD) scheme in India from 2014-15 to 2022-23. It is found from the table that highest fund utilised by Bihar with 14173.2 lakhs for dairy development, second place was occupied by the Rajasthan with 11097.59 lakhs, and third place is found by Punjab with 7616.34 lakhs total utilised amount. It is further noticed that very less amount utilised by some of the states like 42.89 lakhs spent by Puducherry and 84.63 lakhs spent by Goa state. It is unfortunate- some of the states have huge unspent amount which are found that 3406.36lakhs by Uttar Pradesh, followed by Bihar is 3149.94 lakhs and Kerala with 1777.67 lakhs in India.

IV. PROBLEMS OF DAIRY INDUSTRY IN INDIA

1. Climatic Changes: In India climate plays main role in every field when there is good monsoon, automatically agriculture field is affected there is sudden economic growth due to weather changes dairy industry is also stimulated in India. Country have monsoon generally between June and September. It covers about 100 to 120 days in the year during which the country gets 73.7 percent of the total rainfall when there is little rainfall or a drought the number of cattle is driven off from drought distracted areas. In such situations the feed and fodder becomes short and the yield of the milk also goes down. Due to this one can

say that agriculture and milk industry are connected to each other and climate plays significant role.

2. Transportation problem: In the development of any industry transportation plays very important role all after production when supplied in time at market can get good price is the pure logic in order to balance the demand and supply of product transportation plays the important. Regularly milk is collected from villages different area is brought to the dairy industry where milk is processed and then packed for selling in market.

3. Costing of Milk Production: Generally milk is collected from one place and then brought to the dairy industry. It is perceptible that the price given to the farmer or the owner of cow and buffalo for the milk supplied is very less. However the middle men takes major share of money in dairy industry from same milk lot of variety is prepared and just left behind milk that is toned milk is sold at heavy rates this trend of the owner of dairy unit increases the production cost the income of the dairy holder is increased but public has to face the problem of this heavy cost.

4. Formation of Various Milk Society: In villages there are more than one society those who collect the milk from farmers but due to this farmers are confuse to whom they should sell their milk . Various society prices per liter of milk are different.

5. Formation of Milk Unions: In district or villages where there are number of societies automatically there create number of milk unions. Due to personal oppositions many of them have to appearance difficulties in payment of monthly milk income.

6. Marketing of the Product: Milk or dairy units are now facing vast competition among themselves various milk brands, quality changes special effects the mentality of human beings also “tetra” packaging milk is affecting the milk units for the combative sell in market.

7. Unemployment and Poor Living Style: Indian farmers are hard worker and they put their long hours all the year in farming. They are poor and their cattle are also ill managing and ill care. The area of land with farmer is generally small and he keeps one or two milk

cattle's. He is poor and his resources are limited, this limits his creditworthiness. Due to this poor living style, milk units are unnatural the quality of milk and quality of milk both are reduced also to be financially solid people migrate to city hence unemployment problem is seen on big in villages.

8. Political Intervention: Another major problem that Indian dairy industry is facing political interference in day to day life due to personal opponents there is always fights, quarrels among any two units, owners or employee .This political intervention more effects dairy industry.

9. Poor Genetic Problem and Absence of New Technology: The main problem which is arising for dairy farmers is low productivity, the reasons found are as follow there is lack of knowledge of technical know to how cattle are suffering from poor genetic potential, there is insufficient health coverage being villages, also there is shortage of water and fodder which affects the milk productivity among cattle's.

CONCLUSION

Today Indian dairy industry contributes significantly to GDP and Agricultural GDP it also provides employment and economic assistance for millions of people. India has become the largest producer of milk in world and is the largest consumer of milk. Despite this enormous success in dairy development Indian dairy industry also marked by several challenges which are constantly hindering its further development. The organized sector has limited coverage of dairy industry it needs to step up to increase its coverage and the benefits of dairy development should be reached to the rural producers which are the main contributors to the dairy development of India.

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